

DISTRIBUTION OF UNIONIDAE AND CORBICULIDAE FAMILIES IN WATER BODIES AND THEIR COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *In the given paper has shown that 5 species are distributed in the Pachkamar Reservoir, 7 species and 2 subspecies in the Todakol Reservoir, and 9 species and 1 subspecies in the Tuyamuyin Reservoir. It has been established that the Shannon biodiversity index value in the reservoirs is 1.5 in Pachkamar Reservoir, 2.0 in Todakul Reservoir, and 2.1 in Tuyamuyin Reservoir. We have studied the belonging of these species to pelorheophilic, rheophilic, and pelolemnophilic ecological groups. When studying the distribution of bivalve mollusks of the Unionidae and Corbiculidae families in reservoirs and their comparative analysis, it was found that the number and density of species in Pachkamar Reservoir on the shore of Kashkadarya are less than in other reservoirs. We have analyzed that Todakol and Tuyamuyin Reservoirs are rich in species and have a high density. The reason is that these reservoirs affect the biodiversity of these species located in the lower reaches of Zarafshan and Amu Darya rivers.*

Keywords: *reservoir, Sinanodonta gibba, Colletopterum bactrianum, Colletopterum ponderosum volgense, Colletopterum cyreum sogdianum, rocky biotopes.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that in the world, global warming causes seasonal changes in the water level of reservoirs located in arid regions, and a crisis of biological diversity in them. At the moment, mollusks are acquiring special significance as hydrobionts sensitive to the impact of abiotic and anthropogenic factors, and a transformation of their populations is observed depending on the hydrological regime of reservoirs and water pollution. Periodic inventory of malacofauna of poorly studied water bodies, determination of factors influencing their population, assessment of the state of rare, endemic and economically important species is of great scientific and practical importance [1,3,4,6,9]. Today, the study of the distribution of bivalve mollusks Unionidae and Corbiculidae in water bodies and their comparative analysis is considered one of the urgent tasks.

Object and methods of the study. During the research in 2019-2024, more than 280 samples were collected and analyzed at Pachkamar, Todakol and Tuyamuyin reservoirs. The

materials were collected according to the method of Izzatullayev, Boymurodov (2019,2023,2024) [2,5,7,8].

Research results and their analysis. During the study, the distribution of bivalve mollusks of the Unionidae and Corbiculidae families in the Pachkamar, Todakol and Tuyamuyin reservoirs was carried out, their comparative analysis was carried out, and we will give information about them.

Pachkamar reservoir has been built on the bank of Guzor River. The reservoir is filled with water from Kattaora and Kichikora rivers. The total length of the reservoir is on average 3.8 km, the width is 1.9 km. The area of the water surface is 13.7 km², the depth is 52 m, the average depth is 32 m. The type of water constantly regulates the perennial water regime of the river.

Besides that, of great importance is the comprehensive study of the fauna of bivalve mollusks of the reservoirs of Kashkadarya basin in Central Asia. The diversity of natural conditions of the aquatic ecosystem has led to the spread of rare, endemic and relict species. Along with the complex distribution of species in aquatic ecosystems, faunistic complexes, there are differences in the ecology of different populations of the same species.

A special study of the fauna and species diversity of the water bodies of Kashkadarya basin, including Pachkamar reservoir, important bioecological features in individual biogeocenoses, and patterns of species distribution has theoretical and practical significance.

By this time, we had information on some taxonomic positions and ecological features of large bivalves of Kashkadarya basin from I. Zhadin (1952), Z. Izzatullayev (1980), Ya. Starobogatov, Z. Izzatullayev (1984). Small bivalves of the Pisididae and Euglesidae families, common in springs and sources of Kashkadarya basin, have not been studied. No special studies on the bivalves of Pachkamar reservoir have been conducted.

As a result of our studies, 9 species and 1 subspecies were studied in Pachkamar reservoir

(Table 1).

№	Species	Pachkamar Reservoir	Tudakol Reservoir	Tuyamuyin Reservoir	Ecological groups
	Unionidae family				
1.	<i>Sinanodonta gibba</i>	-	1,1±0,1	1,0±0,1	Peloreofil
2.	<i>Sinanodonta orbicularis</i>	0,7±0,2	-	0,9±0,1	Peloreofil
3.	<i>Sinanodonta puerorum</i>	0,6±0,1	1,0±0,1	0,8±0,1	Peloreofil
4.	<i>Colletopterum bactrianum</i>	-	0,3±0,1	0,4±0,1	Reofil
5.	<i>Colletopterum cyreum sogdianum</i>	-	0,2±0,1	-	Reofil
6.	<i>Colletopterum ponderosum volgense</i>	-	0,9±0,1	0,6±0,1	Pelolimnofil
	Corbiculidae family				
7.	<i>Corbicula cor</i>	-	0,4±0,1	0,6±0,1	Peloreofil
8.	<i>Corbicula fluminalis</i>	0,4±0,1	-	0,3±0,1	Peloreofil
9.	<i>Corbicula purpurea</i>	-	0,6±0,1	0,5±0,1	Peloreofil

10.	<i>Corbiculina tibetensis</i>	1,4±0,2	2,3±0,2	2,4±0,3	Peloreofil
11.	<i>Corbiculina ferghanensis</i>	1,3±0,2	2,4±0,2	2,1±0,2	Peloreofil
	Total:	5	9	10	

Moreover, the humpback whale plays an important role in the distribution of bivalves. White carp is a species of the Cyprinidae family. It is widely distributed in the central and northern reservoirs of China. It was brought to Central Asia, in particular to Uzbekistan, in 1960-1963 and acclimatized. It passed from Amu Darya through Amu Darya Canal to the reservoirs of Zarafshan River and through Karshi Main Canal to the reservoir in Kashkadarya basin.

It is worth mentioning that Chinese toothless clam: *Sinanodonta orbicularis*, *Spuerorum*, were got to Pachkamar reservoir during the acclimatization of silver carp. Larvae of Chinese toothless (glochidia) parasitize these fish. Currently, these mollusks are widespread in all artificial and natural reservoirs of Uzbekistan. In nature, it grows in the lower reaches of Amu Darya and in the waters of Syr Darya. In Pachkamar reservoir, *Sinanodonta puerorum* is 0.6 pcs. per 1 m² at depths of 1-2.5 m. The water temperature of Pachkamar reservoir affects not only the growth and reproduction of mollusks, but also plays an important role in their distribution and territorial distribution in the reservoir. The reservoir of *Synanodonta orbicularis* averaged 0.7 individuals per 1 m², distributed in the biotopes of the right bank. *Sinanodonta gibba*, *Colletopterum bactrianum*, *Colletopterum ponderosum volgense* and *Colletopterum cyreum sogdianum* were not found in the reservoir [2,7,5]. It was established that *Corbicula fluminalis* 0.4, *Corbiculina ferghanensis* 1.3 and *C. tibetensis* 1.4 are distributed in the sandy and rocky biotopes of the reservoir.

Definitely, Todakol Reservoir is located in the Navoi Region, in a natural stream 26 km east of Bukhara, and was commissioned in 1968. The total volume is 800 million m³, the surface area is 17.5 km², and the average depth is 4.8 m. The height of the dam is 4 m, and the maximum water flow is 46.0 m³/s. It collects excess water from Zarafshan River through Ordachol Canal, and is filled from Amu Darya through Amu-Bukhara Automobile Canal. Fishing is carried out in Todakol Reservoir. Todakol Reservoir receives water from Zarafshan and Amu Darya Rivers through Amu-Bukhara Canal and is richer in mollusc species than other reservoirs. As a result of our previous studies and our research, it was established that Todakol Reservoir is home to 7 species and 2 subspecies of bivalve mollusks belonging to the Unionidae and Corbiculidae families, which belong to two families and 4 genera (Table 1). The Unionidae family, the *Sinanodonta* genus, *Sinanodonta gibba*, *S. puerorum* are common in the upper reaches of Todakol Reservoir and are rare compared to other species. Two factors have a great influence on the distribution of *Sinanodonta* species in the reservoir. Species of the *Sinanodonta* and *Colletopterum* genera have migrated to Todakol Reservoir along with water and fish. Secondly, white amur and *dungpeshana* are acclimatizing in Todakol Reservoir on the bank of Zarafshan River. With the help of these fish, China led to the spread of mollusks.

Because these fish are parasitized by *Sinanodonta gylodia*. The species scattered in the reservoir have different densities. *Synanodonta gibba* is distributed on average from 1.1 and *S. puerorum* from 1.0 per 1 m².

The seeds of *Colletopterum*, *Colletopterum bactrianum*, *C. cyreum sogdianum* and *C. ponderosum volgense* are distributed in the swampy biotopes of the reservoir.

Among these species, the density of the subspecies *C. cyreum sogdianum* is lower than that of other species - 0.2 per 1 m². We noticed that the other species - *Colletopterum bactrianum* 0.3, *C. ponderosum volgense* 0.9.

However, mollusks are numerous in the silty and microphyte-rich parts of the reservoir. Here they live at depths of 1-2.5 m in reeds and algae, and sometimes in sandy, rocky areas. Their density per 1 m² was *Corbicula cor* 0.4, *C. purpurea* 0.6, *Corbiculina ferghanensis* 2.4, *C. tibetensis* 2.3. Tuyamoin Reservoir was built in 1963 in the lower reaches of Amu Darya. It serves for seasonal regulation of Amu Darya water for irrigation and energy purposes. Volume - 7800 million m³. Z.I. Izzatullayev (2000, 2008) in his studies showed that *C. cyreum sogdianum* is widespread in Tuyamoin Reservoir.

Currently, 9 species and 1 subspecies of bivalve mollusks of the families Unionidae and Corbiculidae inhabit the aquatic ecosystems of the reservoir (Table 1). *Sinanodonta orbicularis* 0.9, *S. puerorum* 0.8 and *S. gibba* 1.0, *Colletopterum bustrianum* 0.4 and *Colletopterum ponderosum volgense* 0.6 were found in the Umomoin Reservoir. It was established that *Corbicula cor*, *Corbicula fluminalis*, *C. purpurea*, *Corbiculina ferghanensis* and *C. tibetensis* occur on average 0.3-2.4 per 1 m². Changes in the balance of aquatic ecosystems of reservoirs, in particular, disruption of the water hydroregime, to a certain extent affect the number and density of the studied species of bivalve mollusks.

Table 2. Biodiversity indicators of mollusks common in Pachkamar, Tudakol, and Tuyamuyin reservoirs, according to the Shannon index.

Indicators	Pachkamar Reservoir	Tudakol Reservoir	Tuyamuyin Reservoir
Number of common species	5	9	10
Number of individuals	44	72	98
Value of Shannon index	1,5	2,0	2,1

While comparing the Shannon index of biodiversity in water bodies, we found that it is 1.5 in Pachkamar Reservoir, 2.0 in Todakol Reservoir, and 2.1 in Tuyamuyin Reservoir (Table 2).

Besides that, natural fluctuations in the abundance of model mollusk species are observed in unstable ecosystem conditions. Under conditions of environmental transformation, changes are observed in the taxonomic structure of the bivalve fauna (a decrease in the abundance of stenobionts and narrow-range, rare, and endangered species affected by anthropogenic factors).

Conclusion. As a result of our research, the distribution of 5 species in Pachkamar Reservoir, 7 species and 2 subspecies in Todakol Reservoir, 9 species and 1 subspecies in Tuyamuyin Reservoir was established. We studied the belonging of these species to pelorheophilic, rheophilic, and pelolemnophilic ecological groups. When studying the distribution of bivalve mollusks of the families Unionidae and Corbiculidae in water bodies and their comparative analysis, it was found that the number and density of species in Pachkamar reservoir on the shore of Kashkadarya is less than in other water bodies. We analyzed that Todakol and Tuyamuyin reservoirs are rich in species and have a high density. The reason is that these reservoirs affect the biodiversity of these species located in the lower reaches of Zarafshan and Amu Darya rivers.

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